

Kinetic Expressions, Their Evaluated Values for the Thermodynamic Rate Constants, the L^s , in Electroosmosis and Some Membrane Parametric Information

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Manuscript received 24 March 1981, accepted 11 August 1981

Classical parametric expressions for the various rate constants, the L^s , in electroosmosis have been used in combination with their values obtained experimentally or otherwise to obtain the membrane parametric information r/l and nr (where n , r and l stand for average number, radius and length of the capillaries) for a number of composite membranes. The results agree well with the ones obtained by a different procedure. They also testify the adequacy of the L^s expressions.

INVESTIGATIONS in transport processes through artificial membranes have aroused considerable interest in recent years as apart from giving an insight into the mechanism¹⁻⁶ of the process and acting as models for biological systems⁷⁻¹² they throw light on internal structure¹³⁻²² of a membrane in terms of certain parameters. Solomon²³ has critically discussed the significance of information about the parameters n , r and l which stand respectively for the average number, average radius and the average length of the capillaries constituting a membrane which has been defined in many ways²⁴⁻³⁵. A number of methods are available for this evaluation¹³⁻²³. Jha *et al.*²², by using the steady state electroosmotic pressure data obtained from a single set of experiments, have been able to evaluate separately the values of n , r and l for a composite membrane. The validity of the method has been tested in an earlier analysis^{22(a),(b)} for two composite membranes^{26(a),(b)}. Other methods, however, suffer from the disadvantage that they use the data obtained from experiments of different types and hence are complicated. In this communication an attempt has been made to obtain membrane parametric information of some kind following a different procedure making use of the expressions²² for various orders of L^s values in the matter flux, J , in electroosmosis in combination with various order L^s values obtained experimentally or otherwise for (a) examining the adequacy and competence of the method and (b) to find whether the current analysis can give any information regarding the accuracy of the higher order L^s values reported earlier²⁶.

Results and Discussions

Evaluation of r/l : A look into the kinetic expressions²² for various order thermodynamic rate constants, the L^s , in electroosmosis would suggest the feasibility of obtaining the membrane parametric value, r/l , for a composite membrane if we have values, experimental or otherwise, for various orders of L^s for it. Equating the various terms given in kinetic parameters in the expression²² for J , the matter flux in

electroosmosis, with those of the corresponding thermodynamic quantities, L^s , associated with correspondingly the like orders of Δp and $\Delta\phi$ we obtain the following relations for a membrane

$$\frac{nr^4}{l^3} = \frac{L_{1,2} \cdot 4 \cdot 8^3 \cdot \pi^2 \cdot \eta^4 k}{\rho \cdot \xi^3 \cdot D^3} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\frac{nr^2}{l} = \frac{L_{1,2} \cdot 4 \cdot \eta}{\xi \cdot D} \quad \dots (2)$$

and the like in association with various concerned L^s values for the membrane system. ρ , D , η and k in the above equations have their usual significance being respectively equal to density, dielectric constant, viscosity and specific electrical conductivity of the permeant and ξ stands for the zeta potential at solid (membrane)/permeant interface. The values of $L_{1,2}$, $L_{1,2}$ etc. for a system (pyrex sinter/acetone) using five similar composite membranes²⁶ (pyrex sinter, porosity G-4) are available²⁶ and the values of other parameters in the r.h.s. of equations 1, 2 etc. can be had from literature^{22,26-30}. Hence the quantity in the l.h.s. of equations 1, 2 etc. can be computed. The value thus obtained from equations 1 and others when separately divided by the individual values obtained from equations 2 etc. as indicated in Table 1 gives us values for $(r/l)^2$ from which the membrane parametric quantity r/l is easily computed. This finds place in Table 1 for all the five membranes²⁶.

Evaluation of nr : Another membrane parametric quantity, nr , for a membrane could be obtained by feeding the computed r/l value for the membrane and the literature values^{22,26-30} of the various associated classical parameters appearing in the r.h.s. of equations 1, 2 ... etc. For example, if we divide the computed values of the quantity in the r.h.s. of equations 1 and 2 respectively by the computed values of $(r/l)^3$ and (r/l) we obtain the value of the quantity, nr , for a membrane. This would be clear by examining Table 1 in which nr values obtained variously for five different membranes²⁴ are also listed.

TABLE 1—MEMBRANE PARAMETRIC VALUES r/l AND nr FOR FIVE PYREX GLASS G-4 MEMBRANES

Expressions	values of L^s					r/l values by the use of the values given in columns			
	L_{12}	L_{112}	L_{122}	L_{1112}	L_{1122}	3 & 2	4 & 2	5 & 3	
	$\frac{nr^2 \xi D}{4\eta l}$	$\frac{nr^4 \rho \xi^2 D^2}{4.8^2 \pi^2 \eta^2 k l^2}$	$\frac{nr^4 \rho \xi^2 D^2}{2.8^2 \pi \eta^2 l^2}$	$\frac{3nr^6 \rho^2 \xi^4 D^4}{5 \pi^4 \eta^2 k^2 l^4}$	$\frac{3nr^6 \rho^2 \xi^4 D^4}{2.8^4 \pi^2 \eta^2 k l^4}$				
Experimental	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Membrane I	1.13×10^{-4}	20.2×10^{-10}	6.60×10^{-8}	3.64×10^{-14}	2.12×10^{-12}	5.5×10^{-1}	2.1×10^{-1}	4.5×10^{-1}	
Membrane II	0.94×10^{-4}	19.1×10^{-10}	10.6×10^{-8}	3.26×10^{-14}	2.28×10^{-12}	5.9×10^{-1}	2.86×10^{-1}	4.42×10^{-1}	
Membrane III	0.72×10^{-4}	17.7×10^{-10}	9.6×10^{-8}	2.8×10^{-14}	3.00×10^{-12}	6.5×10^{-1}	3.1×10^{-1}	4.25×10^{-1}	
Membrane IV	1.07×10^{-4}	13.1×10^{-10}	10.7×10^{-8}	0.70×10^{-14}	6.68×10^{-12}	4.58×10^{-1}	2.69×10^{-1}	2.47×10^{-1}	
Membrane V	0.97×10^{-4}	12.1×10^{-10}	12.00×10^{-8}	1.4×10^{-14}	9.96×10^{-12}	4.62×10^{-1}	3.0×10^{-1}	3.6×10^{-1}	
	nr values by the use of values given in columns								
	6 & 4	7 & 2	7 & 3	8 & 2	8 & 4	9 & 5	10 & 6		
	10	11	12	13	14	15	16		
Membrane I	4.3×10^{-1}	1.5×10^{-1}	1.6×10^{-1}	4.0×10^{-1}	3.8×10^{-1}	2.88×10^{-1}	0.45×10^{-1}		
Membrane II	3.5×10^{-1}	1.2×10^{-1}	1.3×10^{-1}	2.4×10^{-1}	2.5×10^{-1}	2.83×10^{-1}	1.34×10^{-1}		
Membrane III	4.22×10^{-1}	0.8×10^{-1}	0.82×10^{-1}	1.7×10^{-1}	1.74×10^{-1}	2.96×10^{-1}	0.7×10^{-1}		
Membrane IV	5.9×10^{-1}	1.74×10^{-1}	1.75×10^{-1}	2.96×10^{-1}	2.97×10^{-1}	11.15×10^{-1}	0.29×10^{-1}		
Membrane V	6.9×10^{-1}	1.56×10^{-1}	1.58×10^{-1}	2.4×10^{-1}	2.4×10^{-1}	3.2×10^{-1}	0.2×10^{-1}		
	Values of $r/l^{2.2(a)}$		Values of $nr^{2.2(a)}$						
Membrane ³⁶ IV	2.54×10^{-1}		3.6×10^{-1}						
Membrane ³⁶ V	2.34×10^{-1}		3.2×10^{-1}						

A glance at the values for the membrane parametric quantities r/l and nr obtained by the present method would indicate that in most of the cases the values are fairly close to the values obtained for two^{36(a),(b)} of the above five similar membranes³⁶ (IV and V) from the individually computed values of r, l and n obtained by analysing²² the available electroosmotic pressure data in the light of the electroosmotic matter flux expression²³ for each of the above two membranes. For easy reference they are also noted in the foot-note of Table 1. The results obtained are encouraging and satisfactory in view of the difficulties and uncertainties involved in these experiments. The adequacy of the evaluation of the membrane parametric quantities r/l and nr by the above methods thus becomes apparent and so becomes of the expression²² for the electroosmotic matter flux J . However, in a few cases there is some divergence e.g. the membrane parametric value for membrane IV in column 15 and for membrane I, III, IV and V in column 16. Looking from the other side of the matter, these disagreements may also, in a sense, indicate the amount of error involved in the evaluation of L_{1112}/T^2 in one case (membrane IV) and L_{1122}/T^2 in almost each case of the membranes³⁶. The genuineness of the discrepancy for the nr value in column¹⁵ becomes a bit more clarified and explained when we examine the L_{1112}/T^2 values for all the five membranes³⁶. This value, in the case of membrane³⁶ (IV), drops down abruptly to a much lesser value as compared to the values for other similar membranes³⁶ thus causing a departure from the expected agreement from other nr values for the rest of the membranes³⁶ because of the involvement of this quantity in the

evaluation of nr given in this column. Similarly, there is a chance of the involvement of greater amount of uncertainty in the determination of L_{1122}/T^2 (the quantity which is made use of in the computational evaluation of nr for all the membranes³⁶) because of two reasons: (1) the uncertainty in the evaluation of total J and (2) mostly due to the uncertainty involved in the analytical evaluation of L_{1122}/T^2 . The only fair agreement of this computed quantity for membrane II recorded in column 16 may therefore be considered just as a coincidence.

Acknowledgement

One of us (S.N.J) is thankful to the U.G.C. for the award of a Teacher Fellowship.

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